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***Dysphania ambrosioides* (L.) Mosyakin and Clemants (Amaranthaceae): An addition to the Flora of Allahabad District, Uttar Pradesh**

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Abstract- Family Amaranthaceae have been explored extensively in Uttar Pradesh. *Dysphania ambrosioides* of family Amaranthaceae is found a new addition to the flora of Allahabad district (Prayagraj) of Uttar Pradesh. The present paper deals with its detailed description, updated citation, phenology, habit, distribution and photographs.

Key words: *Dysphania ambrosioides*, Amaranthaceae, Flora, Prayagraj district, Uttar Pradesh.

INTRODUCTION

Family Amaranthaceae comprises 174 genera and 2500 species distributed extensively in tropical and temperate region of the world. Flora of British India^{1,2} is represented with 37 genera and 97 species, Flora of Upper Gangetic Plain^{3,4} by 14 genera and 28 species, Flora of Uttar Pradesh⁵ by 17 genera 36 species and Flora of Allahabad⁶ is represented by 10 genera 23 species including family Chenopodiaceae.

During floristic exploration of district Prayagraj *Dysphania ambrosioides* of family Amaranthaceae was collected from Phaphamau and it was found that this genus and species are new addition to Flora of Allahabad (Prayagraj) district. *D. ambrosioides* is popularly known as epazote, Mexican tea, American wormseed, paico, mastruz and erva-de-Santa-Maria. The species is native to Central and South America, originated from Mexico. It has spontaneous growth in tropical and subtropical regions

(mainly America and Africa) and also in temperate zones (from the Mediterranean to Central Europe).⁷ It distributed extensively in Brazil occurring in almost all the territory.^{8,9}

MATERIALS & METHODS

Several field trips were undertaken for the study of family Amaranthaceae in district Prayagraj of Uttar Pradesh. The specimens collected were identified with the help of various flora and online herbarium specimen of Royal Botanical Garden, Kew England (K). Voucher specimens are recorded with their name, locality, date and made herbarium by standard methodology.¹⁰ These herbarium specimens were deposited at Duthie Herbarium (DUTHIE), Department of Botany, University of Allahabad, Prayagraj.

Dysphania ambrosioides (L.) Mosyakin & Clemants, Ukrajins'k. Bot. Zurn. 59(4): 382. 2002; Khanna, Geophytology 47(1): 97. 2017. *Chenopodium ambrosioides* L., Sp. Pl. 219. 1753; Hook. f., Fl. Brit. India 5: 4. 1886.

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Herbs or undershrub's, annual, erect, strongly aromatic; stems sparsely pubescent. Leaves oblong or lanceolate, 5-10 x 3-5 cm, obtuse at apex, attenuate at base; lower leaves subentire to shallowly serrate-dentate; upper entire. Flowers in dense glomerulus or paniculate, interrupted spikes, sessile. Tepals green, 4-5, connate at base, ovate-deltoid, 1mm long, hairy outside. Stigma 3-5. Utricles enclosed by tepals. Seed horizontal or vertical, orbicular, 1 mm across, reddish brown, smooth.

Type: HT: LINN 313/13 in Mexico, Lusitania.

Flowering and fruiting: February - April.

Phaphamau, (Prayagraj), Sadhana: 34182 (DUTHIE).

Ecology

Sandy and moist soil and on riverside association with *Croton bonplandianus* Baill., and *Parthenium hysterophorus* L.

Distribution

Africa, Europe, America, Australia, New Zealand, Asia: India: Maharashtra, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, Kerala, Assam, Bihar, Meghalaya, Uttar Pradesh: Aligarh, Bahraich, Bijnor, Bulandshahar, Kanpur, Lucknow, Muzaffarnagar, Shikohabad.

Figure- 1 *Dysphania ambrosioides* (L.) Mosyakin & Clemants of family Amaranthaceae

- A. Habitat,**
- B. Inflorescence,**
- C. Stem with Leaf**

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Morphologically *Dysphania ambrosioides* is closely related to the *D. anthelmintica*. The characteristic feature of identification of these plants is presence of leaves on main stems.

Dysphania ambrosioides (L.) is segregate from *D. anthelmintica* (L.) due to presence of leafless inflorescence, at least in the upper half (sometimes small bracts are present but usually not subtending glomerules.¹¹ *Dysphania anthelmintica* inflorescence leafy to the top (glomerules sub-tended by leaf-like bracts).

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REFERENCE

1. **Hooker J. D. 1885.** *Flora of British India* Vol. 4. L. Reeve, London.
2. **E-flora of India. (2006 onwards).** *An online database of Indian plants developed by the members of e flora of India* Google group (eFIG). <http://sites.google.com/site/efloraofindia/> (Accessed on 25 July 2016).
3. **Duthie J. F. 1903-1923.** *Flora of Upper Gangetic Plain and of the adjacent Siwalik and Sub- Himalayan tracts.* 3 (3rd Vol. completed by R.N. Parkar & W.B. Turril). Office of the supt. of Govt. Print, Calcutta.
4. **Raizada M. B. 1976.** *Supplement to Duthie's flora of the Upper Gangetic Plain and of the adjacent Siwalik and Sub himalayan Tracts.* Bishen Singh Mahendra Pal Singh Dehradun.
5. **Sinha G. P. and Shukla A. P. 2020.** *Flora of Uttar Pradesh Araliaceae – Ceratophyllaceae* vol. 2. Botanical Survey of India, Kolkata
6. **Misra B. K. & Verma B. K. 1992.** *Flora of Allahabad district,* Uttar Pradesh, India. Bishen Singh Mahendra Pal Singh, Dehradun.
7. **Kismann K. G. 1991.** *Plantas infestantes e nocivas.* BASF Brasileira, Sao Paulo
8. **Matos F. D. A., Sousa M. P., Craveiro A. A., & Matos M. E. O. 2004.** *Constituintes químicos ativos e propriedades biológicas de plantas medicinais brasileiras.* Editora UFC, Fortaleza.
9. **Baracuhy José Geraldo de Vasconcelos, Furtado Dermeval Araújo, Francisco Paulo Roberto Megna, Lima José Luciano Santos de, Pereira Jógerson Pinto Gomes (organizadores). 2016.** *Plantas medicinais de uso comum no Nordeste do Brasil.* 2.ed. Campina Grande - PB: EDUFCEG, ISBN: 978-85-8001-163-0. Disponível em:
- 10 **Jain S. K. and Rao R. R. 1977.** *A Handbook of field and Herbarium methods.* Today and Tomorrow's Print and Publ. New Delhi.
11. **Clemants S. E. & Mosyakin S. L. 2003.** *Flora of North America* vol. 4. Oxford University Press, *Flora of North America* Editorial Committee (eds.), North America.
